

Base Economic Analysis of Banyuwangi District

Lintangsari Susanto Putri

Economic and Business, Sebelas Maret University, Surakarta, 57126, Indonesia

ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
05 September 2023

Corresponding Author:
Lintangsari Susanto Putri

ABSTRACT

During its development, Banyuwangi government has taken many ways to increase its economic potential. One of them is the increase in the economy according to the base economy. Banyuwangi has stable 5-year ADHK PDRB results, it's just that there are still two issues, namely strategic issues related to GDP. The strategic issue is economic growth that has not focused on leading sectors which ultimately causes the second issue, namely the not yet optimal contribution of tourism (leading sector) to GDP. The research method used is descriptive quantitative with Location Quotient (SLQ) analysis tool. Based on the results of the research on economic calculations based on Banyuwangi Regency, the data shows that there are 5 basic economic sectors according to business sector.

KEYWORDS: SLQ, business sector.

INTRODUCTION

The territory of Indonesia is an archipelago which has areas with different characteristics. One of the districts in Java Island which has a large area is Banyuwangi Regency. Banyuwangi Regency is the largest area on the island of Java and the second largest fish producing area in Indonesia. This is what makes Banyuwangi has great potential as a region based on agriculture, plantations and fisheries. (Liputan6.com, 2021)

Economic base means according to Zakaria et al (2019) namely opinions regarding development in an area regarding the ability to produce and sell products effectively and efficiently. This model argues that the basic structure consists of two sectors, namely the basic and non-base sectors. Development of the base sector is needed to spur economic growth.

It has been described in research conducted by Zuhdi, (2021) an area is said to have an economic base in a sector when the results of the Location Quotient analysis have a value that a certain sector has shown a basis that has the production results of that sector and has been able to meet the needs of its people so that the surplus obtained can be sold to other regions.

The progress of the regional economy is always accompanied by the achievements of each region in increasing its regional potential. The economy of each region can be seen from the value of GDP (Gross Domestic Product), which is an indicator to see the development of the regional economy in a certain period. In this study, GDP will be used

at constant prices. The use of GDP at a constant price basis is to avoid the instability of the GDP value to be calculated.

During its development, the Banyuwangi Regency government has taken many ways to increase its economic potential. One of them is the increase in the economy according to the base economy. In the opinion of Arsyad 1999 in Job, (2014) The main factor in the economic growth of a region according to economic basis theory is the direct relationship between the region and the outside regarding the demand for goods and services. In addition to having relations between one region and another, the economic sector has interrelationships with one another in a region. This relationship can bring out the power of one sector to another, either directly or indirectly.

Job, (2014) also argues that in regional development, the base economy can be used to see the direction of growth of a region which is determined by producing goods/services and exporting them out of the region. In addition to the base economy, there are also non-base economies, non-base economies also have interests, namely producing goods/ services like the base economy. It's just that its use is used to provide needs in the regional economic area. Calculations regarding basic economic and non-economic basis can be known by using direct and indirect measurements. One of the indirect measurement methods is the Location Quotient method by calculating GDP at constant business field prices.

Through the Location Quotient (LQ) method, we can determine the level of specialization of the base sector by comparing one to another. According to Leigh R.(1970)The use of the location quotient for a particular type of industry in

a given city is: jobs in industry x in city y as a percent of jobs in all industries in y. Then the employment variable in industry x in a country, as a percent of employment in all industries in this country. Several other benchmarks of "all jobs" in cities and nations can be used according to the needs of calculating the growth of a regional economy.

As has been reported in the Banyuwangi District RPJMD for the 2016-2021 period. Banyuwangi has stable PDRB ADHK results for the previous 5 years, it's just that

there are still two issues, namely strategic issues related to GDP. The strategic issue is economic growth that has not focused on leading sectors which ultimately causes the second issue, namely the not yet optimal contribution of tourism (leading sector) to GDP. A part from that, the Banyuwangi district RPJMD also explained that the government would target 3 indicators in the Banyuwangi district GDP. The three indicators are growth in the agricultural, industrial and trade sectors.

Table 1.1 ADHK GDP Growth in Banyuwangi Regency in 2016-2020

Kategori	Lapangan Usaha	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
A	Pertanian	2,81	1,49	-0,73	-0,56	-2,96
B	Pertambangan dan Penggalian	5,09	8,06	6,25	1,93	-7,06
C	Industri Pengolahan	6,17	3,67	7,13	7,86	-0,38
D	Listrik, Gas, dan Air Bersih	4,2	4,37	3,48	3,34	-0,3
E	Pengadaan Air, Pengelolaan Sampah, Limbah dan Daur Ulang	5,05	2,09	4,18	5,31	5,03
F	Konstruksi	7,51	8,08	11,81	12,32	-5,44
G	Perdagangan, Hotel, dan Restoran	6,86	9,12	11,3	9,6	-6,58
H	Transportasi dan Pergudangan	7,68	6,3	5,36	5,97	-12
I	Penyedia Akomodasi dan Makanan	9,5	10,91	10,78	11,18	-13,85
J	Informasi dan Komunikasi	6,92	8,65	8,75	9,03	8,67
K	Jasa Keuangan dan Asuransi	5,8	6,42	6,07	4,2	-0,26
L	Real Estate	5,21	6,37	7,24	6,63	1,91
M,N	Jasa Perusahaan	5,77	6,28	7,15	6,64	-6,13
O	Administrasi Pemerintahan, Pertahanan dan Jaminan Sosial Wajib	5,54	4,45	4,2	2,21	-3,68
P	Jasa Pendidikan	6,57	7,39	7,43	7,14	3,13
Q	Jasa Kesehatan dan Kegiatan Sosial	8,66	9,8	7,61	6,22	15,55
R,S,T,U	Jasa Lainnya	9,02	8,68	9,86	8,16	-13,2

Source: (Banyuwangi Regency Government, 2021)

In line with this, currently Banyuwangi district is according to the RPJMD 2021-2026 (2021) PDRB ADHK results of the previous 5 years. In the previous 5 years, the sectors with the highest growth results were the provision of accommodation and food, construction, trade, hotels and food, information and communication, and health services and social activities. But in recent years health services and social activities have decreased. While the slowest growth in the GDP sector and the trend in the last 2 years has decreased includes the agricultural sector and government administration, defense, and mandatory social security.

Through the problems above, therefore a basic analysis method is needed to find out what sub-sectors have actually increased in the last 6 years, currently counting from 2015 to 2020. Using research data using constant price GDP data according to business sector, the author wants to know Banyuwangi Regency growth over the last eight years using Location Quotient (SLQ) analysis

A. Writing Problems

- 1) How has the sector increased in Banyuwangi in the last 6 years?
- 2) How is the growth of Banyuwangi Regency using Location Quotient (SLQ) analysis?

B. Writing purpose

- 1) To explain the increase in the sector in the last 6 years.
- 2) To explain the economic growth of Banyuwangi Regency with SLQ

METHODS

The research method used is descriptive quantitative with Location Quotient (SLQ) analysis tool. The following is the formula for SLQ analysis:

$$LQ = \frac{Vik/Vk}{Vip/Vp}$$

note:

vik = Value of output (GRDP) of sector i study area k (district/city)

“Base Economic Analysis of Banyuwangi District”

V_k = Total GRDP of all sectors of the study area k(district/city)
 v_{ip} = Value of output (GRDP) of sector i reference area p (province)
 V_p = Total GRDP of all sectors in the reference area p (province)

The data used PDRB data at constant prices by business field for 6 years (2015-2020). The study area of this research is the PDRB data of Banyuwangi Regency with the reference area being the province of East Java. The 17 types of business fields that serve as indicators in this study use GRDP at constant prices. Constant prices are used to avoid volatility in value.(Rahadiantino & Fathurrohman, 2021)

Table 3.1 GDP data at constant prices 2015-2020

Produk Domestik Regional Bruto Atas Dasar Harga Konstan 2019 Menurut Lapangan Usaha (Miliar rupiah), 2015-2019											
Kategori	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2017	2018	2019	2020	2019
A. Persewa	14.951,59	15.570,28	15.602,18	15.491,01	15.406,81	14.990,31	160.189,40	164.762,01	167.860,57	161.798,84	161.951,23
B. Perdagangan dan Persewaan	1.689,70	1.877,61	1.938,08	1.851,01	1.837,88	1.737,40	65.797,81	75.814,89	80.616,18	82.171,56	81.817,02
C. Industri Pengolahan	1.131,73	1.460,39	1.638,48	1.653,06	1.519,09	1.584,10	390.272,89	430.741,11	434.111,18	468.988,34	498.740,33
D. Listrik, Gas, Air Panas	29,87	36,13	37,27	38,33	38,18	39,87	4.411,27	4.401,09	4.899,56	4.486,36	4.961,03
E. Pengangkutan, Pengangkutan Informasi, Komunikasi dan Jasa Keuangan	30,21	31,73	32,46	31,75	35,54	37,33	1.298,27	1.368,67	1.414,64	1.511,81	1.588,75
F. Konstruksi	4.981,41	5.382,88	5.798,26	6.488,38	7.279,34	8.883,85	128.688,27	127.314,64	138.116,39	148.146,26	151.689,38
G. Perdagangan, Hotel, dan Restoran	4.481,20	4.842,62	7.466,41	8.387,66	9.928,39	8.585,87	243.014,88	277.128,68	271.213,45	298.136,36	307.440,92
H. Transpor dan Persewaan	1.283,87	1.383,33	1.488,97	1.546,39	1.611,00	1.605,86	18.891,87	41.111,11	41.813,33	46.712,47	46.471,43
I. Persewa Akomodasi dan Makanan	1.042,82	1.141,97	1.246,53	1.401,58	1.593,99	1.343,84	67.697,84	71.397,92	79.262,19	89.237,56	81.838,18
J. Informasi dan Komunikasi	1.289,44	1.434,39	1.638,57	2.067,27	3.126,18	3.987,31	73.638,96	79.218,94	84.499,11	94.116,22	97.879,63
K. Jasa Keuangan dan Asuransi	791,26	839,18	891,18	965,34	897,16	984,01	34.738,26	37.118,62	38.366,85	38.838,82	41.374,83
L. Real Estate	681,80	727,64	774,02	836,36	881,09	981,87	23.082,84	24.298,54	23.247,60	24.821,87	26.441,39
M. Jasa Persewaan	103,80	109,58	116,47	124,86	133,08	134,81	18.148,89	19.834,75	11.466,87	12.188,51	13.128,02
N. Administrasi Pemerintahan, Pendidikan dan Sains, Sosial dan Kesehatan	960,81	1.041,54	1.067,89	1.131,81	1.258,67	1.135,36	18.216,27	11.468,14	12.309,74	13.710,19	14.984,34
O. Jasa Pendidikan	1.032,33	1.126,26	1.138,94	1.260,73	1.486,45	1.386,44	15.138,67	17.418,78	18.891,69	45.028,23	44.433,96
P. Jasa Kesehatan dan Kegiatan Sosial	183,87	177,84	198,27	116,14	213,11	217,83	8.750,34	9.249,18	9.741,84	16.488,68	11.277,81
Q. Jasa Lainnya	521,89	570,96	628,51	681,71	737,14	640,83	18.174,38	20.298,10	21.203,59	22.138,81	23.812,14
R. S. T. Jasa Lainnya											
PDRB	44.933,93	46.824,38	48.488,44	52.163,78	59.219,68	61.281,11	1.331.376,18	1.469.863,31	1.482.299,98	1.563.441,81	1.649.939,64

Source: processed data (2022)

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

According to Leigh, (1970) if the Location Quotient (LQ) has the assumption that the "normal" urban economy is a microcosm of the national economy, the Location Quotient (LQ) is one particular way of calculating urban activity by showing an activity where the city has a certain specialization of size per sector as a whole . The higher the Location Quotient (LQ), the greater the local specialization in certain types of industries. Then for Location Quotient (LQ) which has a value below unity is said to indicate activities that are relatively underrepresented in the local economy, and which cannot be considered as local specialization activities .

According to BPS in web excerptsBanyuwangi Regency, (2015), The average economic growth rate of Kab.

Banyuwangi in the previous five years recorded higher than the average growth of East Java Province. Apart from that, Setyowati, head of the Banyuwangi Regency public relations department, said that ifEconomic growth in Banyuwangi is supported by basic economic sectors, such as agriculture, forestry, mining, industry, construction, housing and tourism. This proves that five years earlier these 5 sectors supported Banyuwangi's economic growth. In the results of the research on economic calculations based on Banyuwangi Regency, the data shows that there are 5 basic economic sectors according to business field. But the current five-year data has differences in the sectors that have been stated previously.

Table 4.1. Table of data processing SLQ 2015-2020

	Lapangan Usaha	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	rata rata
A	Pertanian	2,78	2,80	2,79	2,82	2,77	2,70	2,78
B	Pertambangan dan Penggalian	1,68	1,55	1,56	1,61	1,62	1,58	1,60
C	Industri Pengolahan	0,39	0,40	0,39	0,39	0,39	0,40	0,39
D	Listrik, Gas, dan Air Bersih	0,17	0,17	0,18	0,19	0,19	0,20	0,18
E	Pengadaan Air, Pengolahan Sampah, Limbah dan Daur Ulang	0,70	0,70	0,67	0,66	0,67	0,68	0,68
F	Konstruksi	1,24	1,26	1,28	1,33	1,41	1,40	1,32
G	Perdagangan, Hotel, dan Restoran	0,79	0,80	0,82	0,85	0,88	0,89	0,84
H	Transportasi dan Pergudangan	0,99	1,02	1,01	1,00	1,02	1,01	1,01
I	Penyedia Akomodasi dan Makanan	0,46	0,47	0,48	0,49	0,51	0,49	0,48
J	Informasi dan Komunikasi	0,92	0,92	0,93	0,95	0,96	0,96	0,94
K	Jasa Keuangan dan Asuransi	0,68	0,68	0,70	0,71	0,71	0,72	0,70
L	Real Estate	0,90	0,90	0,92	0,92	0,93	0,92	0,91
M,N	Jasa Perusahaan	0,30	0,30	0,30	0,30	0,30	0,31	0,30
O	Administrasi Pemerintahan, Pertahanan dan Jaminan Sosial Wajib	0,98	0,99	1,01	1,00	0,99	0,97	0,99
P	Jasa Pendidikan	1,21	1,22	1,26	1,28	1,28	1,29	1,26
Q	Jasa Kesehatan dan Kegiatan Sosial	0,56	0,58	0,60	0,60	0,59	0,64	0,59
S,T,U	Jasa Lainnya	0,81	0,84	0,88	0,91	0,93	0,95	0,89

Processed data

Calculation of the average LQ method for 2015 - 2020 shows that 5 economic sectors in Banyuwangi Regency are classified in the basic economic sector category with the criteria for the results of the LQ calculation value > 1, namely the agricultural sector with an LQ value (2.78), the mining and quarrying sector with an LQ value (1.60), construction

sector (1.32), transportation and warehousing sector (1.01), education services sector (1.26). The covid pandemic has had an impact on every sector in Banyuwangi Regency. The calculation of the 5 year SLQ 2015 to 2019 shows the results that there are 8 leading sectors which are the base economy in Banyuwangi. The following is the result of the analysis.

Table 4.2. Table of data processing SLQ 2015-2019

	Business field	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	average
A	Agriculture, Forestry, Fisheries	2.75	2.80	2.79	2.82	2.78	2.79
B	Mining and excavation	1.66	1.55	1.56	1.60	1.60	1.59
C	Processing industry	0.39	0.40	0.39	0.38	0.39	0.39
D	Electricity, Gas and Clean Water	4.00	0.17	4.26	4.45	4.54	3.49
E	Water Procurement, Waste Management, Waste and Recycling	16.51	0.70	0.67	15.81	15.89	9.91
F	Construction	1.22	1.26	1.28	1.32	1.40	1.30
G	Trade, Hotels and Restaurants	0.78	0.80	0.82	0.85	0.88	0.82
H	Transportation and Warehousing	0.98	1.02	1.01	0.99	1.01	1.00
I	Accommodation and Food Providers	0.46	0.47	0.48	0.49	0.50	0.48
J	Information and Communication	0.91	0.92	0.93	0.94	0.95	0.93
K	Financial Services and Insurance	0.68	0.68	0.70	0.70	0.71	0.69
L	Real Estate	0.89	0.90	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.91
M N	Company Services	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30
O	Government Administration, Defense and Compulsory Social Security	0.97	0.99	1.01	0.99	0.98	0.99
P	Education Services	1.20	1.22	1.26	1.27	1.27	1.24
Q	Health Services and Social Activities	13.29	13.83	0.60	0.59	0.59	5.78
R,S, T,U	Other Services	0.80	0.84	0.88	0.91	0.92	0.87

Calculation of the average LQ method for 2015 - 2019 shows that 8 economic sectors in Banyuwangi Regency are classified in the basic economic sector category with the

result criteria for the LQ calculation value > 1, namely the agricultural sector with an LQ value (2.79), the mining and quarrying sector with an LQ value (1.59), the electricity, gas

and clean water sector (3.49), the water supply sector, waste management, waste and recycling (9.91), the construction sector (1.30), the education services sector (1.24), health services and social activities (5.78)). Then there are also economic sectors that are at a value of = 1 which are still included in the basic economic category, namely the transportation and warehousing economic sector (1.00). This shows that the growth rate of the 8 sectors in Banyuwangi Regency is greater than the growth rate of the same sector in the economy of East Java Province. This shows that the growth rate of the 3 above sectors is experiencing a setback. And also the five leading sectors in Banyuwangi Regency are bigger than the growth rate of the same sector in the economy of East Java Province.

Through the results of the calculations, the 5 sectors in the previous five year period (2015-2019) were slightly different from the 2015-2020 five year period. In the previous data it was stated that the sectors that support Banyuwangi Regency are agriculture, mining and quarrying, the electricity, gas and clean water sectors, water supply, waste management, waste and recycling, the construction sector, the education services sector, health services and social activities, the economy transportation and warehousing.

Whereas in the current period, through SLQ calculations it is known that the 5 sectors currently referred to are agriculture, mining and quarrying, construction, transportation and warehousing, education services.

If in the pre-pandemic results, strategic problems/strategic issues in the RPJMD can be seen if economic growth is still not focused on leading sectors. This is evidenced by the sector Trade, Hotels and Restaurants which have an average value (0.82). Hotels and restaurants are one of the indicators to assess the income of the tourism sector in addition to the number of tourists. Then the RPJMD also mentions strategic issues, namely not yet optimal contribution of tourism (leading sector) to GDP. This occurs as an impact of the previous base economic value.

In addition, the RPJMD of Banyuwangi Regency also explained that the government would target 3 indicators in Banyuwangi Regency's GRDP. The three indicators are growth in the agricultural, industrial and trade sectors. Through the basic economic data above, it can be seen that the growth that has exceeded the current target is agriculture with a value of 2.79. Whereas the 2 previous sectors described in the 2010-2014 period were one of the pillars of Banyuwangi's economic growth, in the current period they have a base value of <1.

Water Procurement, Waste Management, Waste and Recycling is a priority sector in the data above, with a value of 9.91. In its implementation, the government of Banyuwangi Regency through DLH implemented a waste bank. The waste bank is an assessment of used / discarded goods denominated in money. The results obtained will be saved later and can then be disbursed when the big day

arrives. For example, when it comes to commemorating Eid. This kind of application is considered quite effective in inviting the community to join in managing waste, waste and recycling. At the location around the author there is also a garbage bank post which will then be deposited with the DLH Banyuwangi Regency to the general waste bank.

Then the second base sector is the health services sector and social activities which has a value of 5.78. This is an unexpected achievement, considering that in the previous period the sector was not the basis of the economy. According to the RPJMD, one of the strategic issues mentions the low level of community access to quality basic needs. The purpose of this low access is the difficulty experienced by the people of Banyuwangi, especially rural areas, to be able to access one of the basic health services. Through the results of these five years, it can be proven that the direction of economic growth in Banyuwangi Regency currently has a basis in health services to deal with this strategic issue.

Next is the electricity, gas and clean water sector (3.49), awareness of the importance of clean water is currently very rare but if we go to the highlands in Banyuwangi, almost all rivers maintain their water quality . This is because water is one of the objects of their business field in the tourism sector. So according to the residents there when they don't take care of the object, of course their business field can also be threatened. The next assessment is on the agricultural sector with a value of LQ (2.79), quoted from the East Java Ministry of Communication and Information, the agricultural sector is the leading sector through PDRB data based on constant prices according to business sector. The determination of the base economy is due to the achievement of agriculture which is always considered a surplus.

CONCLUSIONS

The conclusion from this analysis is that the growth of the 5 sectors in Banyuwangi Regency is superior compared to the same growth rate in East Java Province. But this is a decrease from the previous target which produced 8 leading sectors. If you look at the previous RPJMD, namely 2015-2019, it can be seen that the RPJMD explains that one of Banyuwangi Regency's strategic issues is the low level of community access to clean water and a healthy and quality environment. The majority of the causes of a lack of clean water and a healthy environment are from irregular waste handling and waste management. In addition, the achievement of the 5 basic economic sectors of Banyuwangi Regency is considered to be able to overcome some of the problems that already exist in Banyuwangi Regency's RPJMD.

REFERENCES

1. Ayubi, A. A. (2014). ANALISIS POTENSI EKONOMI KABUPATEN BANYUWANGI. *Jurnal Ekonomi Pembangunan*, 12(1).

- <https://doi.org/10.22219/jep.v12i1.3651>
2. D'Ornay, A., Hasan, M., & Natsir S, U. (2020). ANALISIS PERTUMBUHAN EKONOMI DAN PERGESERAN ANTAR SEKTOR EKONOMI DI KABUPATEN BANGGAI LAUT PROVINSI SULAWESI TENGAH. *Journal of Economic, Public, and Accounting (JEPA)*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.31605/jepa.v3i1.832>
 3. Kabupaten Banyuwangi. (2015). *Pertumbuhan Ekonomi Banyuwangi Lampau Rata-rata Provinsi Jawa Timur*. Kabarpwi. <https://banyuwangikab.go.id/berita/pertumbuhan-ekonomi-banyuwangi-lampau-rata-rata-provinsi-jawa-timur>
 4. Leigh, R. (1970). The Use of Location Quotients in Urban Economic Base Studies. *Land Economics*, 46(2). <https://doi.org/10.2307/3145181>
 5. Liputan6.com. (2021). 6 Fakta Menarik Banyuwangi di Jawa Timur yang Perlu Diketahui. <https://www.liputan6.com/lifestyle/read/4464695/6-fakta-menarik-banyuwangi-di-jawa-timur-yang-perlu-diketahui>
 6. Maghfiroh, A. (2021). Pola Pertumbuhan Perekonomian melalui Sektor Unggulan Daerah Kabupaten Jombang. *Journal of Economic, Management, Accounting and Technology*, 4(2). <https://doi.org/10.32500/jematech.v4i2.1560>
 7. Novita, N., Sari, R. P., & Anwar, R. (2021). IDENTIFIKASI POTENSI SEKTOR EKONOMI BASIS DAN NON BASIS KOTA METRO. *Jurnal Agriovet*, 3(2). <https://doi.org/10.51158/agriovet.v3i2.456>
 8. Nugraha, A. T., Prayitno, G., & Khoiriyah, L. A. (2021). Land suitability and economic performance in the Pasuruan region for coffee development. *International Journal of Sustainable Development and Planning*, 16(2). <https://doi.org/10.18280/IJSDP.160203>
 9. Pemerintah Kabupaten Banyuwangi. (2021). *RENCANA PEMBANGUNAN JANGKA MENENGAH DAERAH KABUPATEN BANYUWANGI TAHUN 2021-2026*. https://banyuwangikab.go.id/media/dokumen/perencanaan/RPJMD_Kabupaten_Banyuwangi_2021-2026.pdf
 10. Rahadiantino, L., & Fathurrohman, J. (2021). Location Quotient Analysis to Facing Competition in The Pandemic Era Of Covid-19 (Case Study : East Java Province). *Jurnal Sosial Humaniora, Special Edition Toward a Post-COVID 19: contributing to individual and social good life*.
 11. Wati, R. M., & Arifin, A. (2019). ANALISIS LOCATION QUOTIENT DAN SHIFT-SHARE SUB SEKTOR PERTANIAN DI KABUPATEN PEKALONGAN TAHUN 2013-2017. *Jurnal Ekonomi-Qu*, 9(2). <https://doi.org/10.35448/jequ.v2i2.7167>
 12. Zakaria, Z., Zulham, T., & Gunawan, E. (2019). ANALISIS STRUKTUR EKONOMI KABUPATEN ACEH BESAR. *JURNAL PERSPEKTIF EKONOMI DARUSSALAM*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.24815/jped.v4i1.10921>
 13. Zuhdi, F. (2021). Peranan Sektor Pertanian terhadap Pertumbuhan Ekonomi Kabupaten Kampar. *Jurnal Ekonomi Pertanian Dan Agribisnis*, 5(1), 274–285. <https://doi.org/10.21776/ub.jepa.2021.005.01.25>
 14. RPJMD Kab Banyuwangi 2016-2021
 15. https://banyuwangikab.go.id/media/dokumen/perencanaan/RPJMD_Kabupaten_Banyuwangi_2021-2026.pdf diakses pada 27/10/22